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Fixed Points for a Pair of F -Dominated Contractive Mappings in Rectangular b -Metric Spaces with Graph

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Abstract: Recently, George et al. (in Georgea, R.; Radenovicb, S.; Reshmac, K.P.; Shuklad, S. Rectangular b -metric space and contraction principles. *J. Nonlinear Sci. Appl.* 2015, 8, 1005–1013) furnished the notion of rectangular b -metric pace (RBMS) by taking the place of the binary sum of triangular inequality in the definition of a b -metric space ternary sum and proved some results for Banach and Kannan contractions in such space. In this paper, we achieved fixed-point results for a pair of F -dominated mappings fulfilling a generalized rational F -dominated contractive condition in the better framework of complete rectangular b -metric spaces complete rectangular b -metric spaces. Some new fixed-point results with graphic contractions for a pair of graph-dominated mappings on rectangular b -metric space have been obtained. Some examples are given to illustrate our conclusions. New results in ordered spaces, partial b -metric space, dislocated metric space, dislocated b -metric space, partial metric space, b -metric space, rectangular metric spaces, and metric space can be obtained as corollaries of our results.

Keywords: fixed point; generalized F -contraction; α_* -dominated mapping; graphic contractions

MSC: 46Txx; 47H10; 54H25

1. Introduction and Preliminaries

Fixed-point theory is a basic tool in functional analysis. Banach [1] has shown significant result for contraction mappings. Due to its significance, a large number of authors have proved newsworthy of this result (see [1–28]). In the sequel George et al. [2] furnished the notion of rectangular b -metric space (RBMS) by taking the place of the binary sum of triangular inequality in the definition of a b -metric space ternary sum and proved some results for Banach and Kannan contractions in such space. Further recent results on rectangular b -metric spaces can be seen in [10,11]. In this paper, we achieved fixed-point results for a pair of α -dominated mappings fulfilling a generalized rational F -dominated contractive condition in complete rectangular b -metric spaces. Therefore, here, we investigate our results in a better framework of rectangular b -metric space. Some new fixed-point results with graphic contractions for a pair of graph-dominated mappings on rectangular b -metric space have been obtained. New results in ordered spaces, partial b -metric space, dislocated metric space, dislocated b -metric space, partial metric space, b -metric space, rectangular metric spaces, and metric space can be obtained as corollaries of our results. First, we give the precise definitions that we will use.

Definition 1 ([2]). Let Z be a nonempty set and let $d_1 : Z \times Z \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ be a function, called a rectangular b -metric (or simply d_1 -metric), if there exists $b \geq 1$ such that the following conditions hold:

- (i) $d_1(g, p) = 0$, if and only if $g = p$;
- (ii) $d_1(g, p) = d_1(p, g)$;
- (iii) $d_1(g, p) \leq b[d_1(g, q) + d_1(q, h) + d_1(h, p)]$ for all $g, p \in Z$ and all distinct points $q, h \in Z \setminus \{g, p\}$. The pair (Z, d_1) is said a rectangular b-metric space (in short R.B.M.S) with coefficient b .

Definition 2 ([2]). Let (Z, d_1) be a R.B.M.S.

- (i) A sequence $\{g_n\}$ in (Z, d_1) said to be Cauchy sequence if for each $\epsilon > 0$, there corresponds $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for all $n, m \geq n_0$ we have $d_1(g_m, g_n) < \epsilon$ or $\lim_{n, m \rightarrow \infty} d_1(g_n, g_m) = 0$.
- (ii) A sequence $\{g_n\}$ rectangular b-converges (for short d_1 -converges) to g if $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d_1(g_n, g) = 0$. In this case, g is called a d_1 -limit of $\{g_n\}$.
- (iii) (Z, d_1) is complete if every Cauchy sequence in Z converges to a point $g \in Z$ for which $d_1(g, g) = 0$.

Example 1 ([2]). Let $Z = \mathbb{N}$ define $d : Z \times Z \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that $d(u, v) = d(v, u)$ for all $u, v \in Z$ and

$$d(u, v) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } u = v; \\ 10\alpha, & \text{if } u = 1, v = 2; \\ \alpha, & \text{if } u \in \{1, 2\} \text{ and } v \in \{3\}; \\ 2\alpha, & \text{if } u \in \{1, 2, 3\} \text{ and } v \in \{4\}; \\ 3\alpha, & \text{if } u \text{ or } v \notin \{1, 2, 3, 4\} \text{ and } u \neq v; \end{cases}$$

where $\alpha > 0$ is a constant. Then (Z, d) is a R.B.M.S with coefficient $b = 2 > 1$, but (Z, d) does not be a rectangular metric, since

$$d(1, 2) = 10\alpha > 5\alpha = d(1, 3) + d(3, 4) + d(4, 2).$$

Definition 3 ([26]). Let (Z, d_1) be a metric space, $S : Z \rightarrow P(Z)$ be a multivalued mapping and $\alpha : Z \times Z \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$. Let $A \subseteq Z$, the mapping S is said semi α_* -admissible on A , if $\alpha(x, y) \geq 1$ implies $\alpha_*(Sx, Sy) \geq 1$, for all $x \in A$, where $\alpha_*(Sx, Sy) = \inf\{\alpha(a, b) : a \in Sx, b \in Sy\}$. When $A = Z$, we say that the S is α_* -admissible on Z . In the case in which S is a single valued mapping, the previous definition becomes.

Definition 4. Let (Z, d_1) be a R.B.M.S. Let $S : Z \rightarrow Z$ be a mapping and $\alpha : Z \times Z \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$. If $A \subseteq Z$, we say that the S is α -dominated on A , whenever $\alpha(i, Si) \geq 1$ for all $i \in A$. If $A = Z$, we say that S is α -dominated.

Definition 5 ([28]). Let (Z, d) be a metric space. A mapping $H : Z \rightarrow Z$ is said to be an A -contraction if there exists $\tau > 0$ such that

$$\forall j, k \in Z, d(Hj, Hk) > 0 \Rightarrow \tau + A(d(Hj, Hk)) \leq A(d(j, k))$$

with $A : \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ real function which satisfies three assumptions:

- (F1) A is strictly increasing
- (F2) For any sequence $\{\alpha_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$ of positive real numbers, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \alpha_n = 0$ is equivalent to $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} A(\alpha_n) = -\infty$;
- (F3) There is $k \in (0, 1)$ for which $\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 0^+} \alpha^k A(\alpha) = 0$.

Example 2 ([19]). Let $Z = \mathbb{R}$. Define the mapping $\alpha : Z \times Z \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ by

$$\alpha(x, y) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x > y \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}.$$

Define the self-mappings $S, T : Z \rightarrow Z$ by $Sx = \frac{x}{4}$, and $Ty = \frac{y}{2}$, where $x, y \in Z$. Suppose $x = 3$ and $y = 2$. As $3 > 2$, then $\alpha(3, 2) \geq 1$. Now, $\alpha(S3, T2) = \frac{1}{2} \not\geq 1$, this means the pair (S, T) is not α -admissible. Also,

$\alpha(S3, S2) \not\geq 1$ and $\alpha(T3, T2) \not\geq 1$. This implies S and T are not α -admissible individually. Now, $\alpha(x, Sx) \geq 1$, for all $x \in Z$. Hence S is α -dominated mapping. Similarly it is clear that $\alpha(y, Ty) \geq 1$ for all $x \in Z$. Hence it is clear that S and T are α -dominated but not α -admissible.

2. Main Result

Theorem 1. Let (Z, d_l) be a complete R.B.M.S with coefficient $b \geq 1$. Let $\alpha : Z \times Z \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ be a function and $S, T : Z \rightarrow Z$ be the α -dominated mappings on Z . Suppose that the following condition is satisfied:

There exist $\tau, \eta_1, \eta_2, \eta_3, \eta_4 > 0$ satisfying $b\eta_1 + b\eta_2 + (1 + b)b\eta_3 + \eta_4 < 1$ and a continuous and strictly increasing real function F such that

$$\tau + F(d_l(Se, Ty)) \leq F \left(\begin{matrix} \eta_1 d_l(e, y) + \eta_2 d_l(e, Se) \\ + \eta_3 d_l(e, Ty) + \eta_4 \frac{d_l^2(e, Se), d_l(y, Ty)}{1 + d_l^2(e, y)} \end{matrix} \right), \tag{1}$$

whenever $e, y \in \{g_n\}$, $\alpha(e, y) \geq 1$ and $d_l(Se, Ty) > 0$ "where the sequence g_n is defined by g_0 arbitrary in Z , $g_{2n+1} = S(TS)^n g_0$ and $g_{2n} = (TS)^{n+1} g_0$ ". Then $\alpha(g_n, g_{n+1}) \geq 1$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$ and $\{g_n\} \rightarrow u \in Z$. Also, if the inequality (1) holds for u and either $\alpha(g_n, u) \geq 1$ or $\alpha(u, g_n) \geq 1$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$, then S and T have a common fixed point u in Z .

Proof. Chose a point g_0 in Z such that $g_1 = Sg_0$ and $g_2 = Tg_1$. Continuing this process we construct a sequence $\{g_n\}$ of points in Z such that $g_{2n+1} = Sg_{2n}$ and $g_{2n+2} = Tg_{2n+1}$ for all for all $n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$. Let $g_1, \dots, g_j \in Z$ for some $j \in \mathbb{N}$. If j is odd, then $j = 2i + 1$ for some $i \in \mathbb{N}$. Since $S, T : Z \rightarrow Z$ be the α -dominated mappings on Z , so $\alpha(g_{2i}, Sg_{2i}) \geq 1$ and $\alpha(g_{2i+1}, Tg_{2i+1}) \geq 1$. As $\alpha(g_{2i}, Sg_{2i}) \geq 1$, this implies $\alpha(g_{2i}, Sg_{2i}) = \alpha(g_{2i}, g_{2i+1}) \geq 1$ where $g_{2i+1} = Sg_{2i}$. Now, by using inequality (1),

$$\begin{aligned} \tau + F(d_l(g_{2i+1}, g_{2i+2})) &\leq \tau + F(d_l(Sg_{2i}, Tg_{2i+1})) \\ &\leq F \left[\begin{matrix} \eta_1 d_l(g_{2i}, g_{2i+1}) + \eta_2 d_l(g_{2i}, Sg_{2i}) + \eta_3 d_l(g_{2i}, Tg_{2i+1}) \\ + \eta_4 \frac{d_l^2(g_{2i}, Sg_{2i}), d_l(g_{2i+1}, Tg_{2i+1})}{1 + d_l^2(g_{2i}, g_{2i+1})} \end{matrix} \right] \\ &\leq F \left[\begin{matrix} \eta_1 d_l(g_{2i}, g_{2i+1}) + \eta_2 d_l(g_{2i}, g_{2i+1}) + b\eta_3 d_l(g_{2i}, g_{2i+1}) \\ + b\eta_3 d_l(g_{2i+1}, g_{2i+2}) + \eta_4 \frac{d_l^2(g_{2i}, g_{2i+1}), d_l(g_{2i+1}, g_{2i+2})}{1 + d_l^2(g_{2i}, g_{2i+1})} \end{matrix} \right] \\ &\leq F[(\eta_1 + \eta_2 + b\eta_3)d_l(g_{2i}, g_{2i+1}) + (b\eta_3 + \eta_4)d_l(g_{2i+1}, g_{2i+2})]. \end{aligned}$$

This implies

$$F(d_l(g_{2i+1}, g_{2i+2})) < F \left[\begin{matrix} (\eta_1 + \eta_2 + b\eta_3)d_l(g_{2i}, g_{2i+1}) \\ + (b\eta_3 + \eta_4)d_l(g_{2i+1}, g_{2i+2}) \end{matrix} \right]$$

As F is strictly increasing. Therefore, we have

$$d_l(g_{2i+1}, g_{2i+2}) < \left[\begin{matrix} (\eta_1 + \eta_2 + b\eta_3)d_l(g_{2i}, g_{2i+1}) \\ + (b\eta_3 + \eta_4)d_l(g_{2i+1}, g_{2i+2}) \end{matrix} \right]$$

Which implies

$$\begin{aligned} (1 - b\eta_3 - \eta_4)d_l(g_{2i+1}, g_{2i+2}) &< (\eta_1 + \eta_2 + b\eta_3)d_l(g_{2i}, g_{2i+1}) \\ d_l(g_{2i+1}, g_{2i+2}) &< \left(\frac{\eta_1 + \eta_2 + b\eta_3}{1 - b\eta_3 - \eta_4} \right) d_l(g_{2i}, g_{2i+1}). \end{aligned}$$

Now, we note that by assumption of inequality (1) it immediately follows $\lambda = \frac{\eta_1 + \eta_2 + b\eta_3}{1 - b\eta_3 - \eta_4} < 1$. Hence

$$d_l(g_{2i+1}, g_{2i+2}) < \lambda d_l(g_{2i}, g_{2i+1}) < \lambda^2 d_l(g_{2i-1}, g_{2i}) < \dots < \lambda^{2i+1} d_l(g_0, g_1).$$

Similarly, if j is even, we have

$$d_l(g_{2i+2}, g_{2i+3}) < \lambda^{2i+2} d_l(g_0, g_1). \tag{2}$$

Now, we have

$$d_l(g_j, g_{j+1}) < \lambda^j d_l(g_0, g_1) \text{ for } j \in \mathbb{N}. \tag{3}$$

Also $\alpha(g_n, g_{n+1}) \geq 1$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$. Now,

$$d_l(g_n, g_{n+1}) < \lambda^n d_l(g_0, g_1) \text{ for all } n \in \mathbb{N}. \tag{4}$$

Now, for any positive integers m, n ($m > n$), we have

$$\begin{aligned} d_l(g_n, g_m) &\leq b[d_l(g_n, g_{n+1}) + d_l(g_{n+1}, g_{n+2}) + d_l(g_{n+2}, g_m)] \\ &\leq b[d_l(g_n, g_{n+1}) + d_l(g_{n+1}, g_{n+2})] + b^2[d_l(g_{n+2}, g_{n+3}) \\ &\quad + d_l(g_{n+3}, g_{n+4}) + d_l(g_{n+4}, g_m)] \\ &\leq b[\lambda^n + \lambda^{n+1}]d_l(g_0, g_1) + b^2[\lambda^{n+2} + \lambda^{n+3}]d_l(g_0, g_1) \\ &\quad + b^3[[\lambda^{n+4} + \lambda^{n+5}]d_l(g_0, g_1) + \dots \\ &\quad + b^{2m-1}\lambda^{m-n}d_l(g_0, g_1), \tag{by (2.4)} \\ &\leq b\lambda^n[1 + b\lambda^2 + b^2\lambda^4 + \dots]d_l(g_0, g_1) \\ &\quad + b\lambda^{n+1}[1 + b\lambda^2 + b^2\lambda^4 + \dots]d_l(g_0, g_1) \\ &\leq \frac{1 + \lambda}{1 - b\lambda^2} b\lambda^n d_l(g_0, g_1). \end{aligned}$$

As $\eta_1, \eta_2, \eta_3, \eta_4 > 0, b \geq 1$ and $b\eta_1 + b\eta_2 + (1 + b)b\eta_3 + \eta_4 < 1$, so $|b\lambda^2| < 1$. Then, we have

$$d_l(g_n, g_m) < \frac{1 + \lambda}{1 - b\lambda^2} b\lambda^n d_l(g_0, g_1) \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty.$$

Hence $\{g_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in Z . Since (Z, d_l) is a complete metric space, so there exist $u \in Z$ such that $\{g_n\} \rightarrow u$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, then

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d_l(g_n, u) = 0. \tag{5}$$

By assumption, $\alpha(u, g_n) \geq 1$. Suppose that $d_l(u, Su) > 0$, then there exists positive integer k such that $d_l(Tg_{2n+1}, Su) > 0$ for all $n \geq k$. For $n \geq k$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} d_l(u, Su) &\leq b[d_l(u, g_n) + d_l(g_n, g_{2n+2}) + d_l(g_{2n+2}, Su)] \\ &\leq b[d_l(u, g_n) + d_l(g_n, g_{2n+1}) + d_l(Tg_{2n+1}, Su)] \\ &\leq b[d_l(u, g_n) + d_l(g_n, g_{2n+1}) + d_l(Su, Tg_{2n+1})] \\ &< b \left[\begin{aligned} &d_l(u, g_n) + d_l(g_n, g_{2n+1}) + \eta_1 d_l(u, g_{2n+1}) \\ &+ \eta_2 d_l(u, Su) + \eta_3 d_l(g_{2n+1}, Tg_{2n+1}) \\ &+ \eta_4 \frac{d_l(u, Su) \cdot d_l^2(g_{2n+1}, Tg_{2n+1})}{1 + d_l^2(g_{2n+1}, u)}. \end{aligned} \right] \end{aligned}$$

Letting $n \rightarrow \infty$, and by using the inequalities (4) and (5) we get

$$d_l(u, Su) < \eta_3 d_l(u, Su) < d_l(u, Su),$$

which is a contradiction. So, our supposition is wrong. Hence $d_1(u, Su) = 0$. Similarly, by using the above inequality

$$\begin{aligned} d_1(u, Tu) &\leq b[d_1(u, g_n) + d_1(g_n, g_{2n+1}) + d_1(g_{2n+1}, Tu)] \\ d_1(u, Tu) &\leq b[d_1(u, g_n) + d_1(g_n, g_{2n+1}) + d_1(Sg_{2n}, Tu)] \end{aligned}$$

we can get $d_1(u, Tu) = 0$. This shows that u is a common fixed point of S and T . \square

Example 3. Let $Z = A \cup B$, where $A = \{\frac{1}{n} : n \in \{2, 3, 4, 5\}\}$ and $B = [1, 2]$. Define $d_1 : Z \times Z \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ such that defined by $d_1(x, y) = d_1(y, x)$ for $x, y \in Z$ and

$$\begin{cases} d_1(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{3}) = d_1(\frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{5}) = 0.03 \\ d_1(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{5}) = d_1(\frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{4}) = 0.02 \\ d_1(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{4}) = d_1(\frac{1}{5}, \frac{1}{3}) = 0.6 \\ d_1(x, y) = |x - y|^2 \quad \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

be the complete R.B.M.S with coefficient $b = 4 > 1$ but (Z, d_1) is neither a metric space nor a rectangular metric space. Take $\eta_1 = \frac{1}{10}, \eta_2 = \frac{1}{20}, \eta_3 = \frac{1}{60}, \eta_4 = \frac{1}{30}, \tau \in (0, \frac{12}{95}]$ then $b\eta_1 + b\eta_2 + (1 + b)b\eta_3 + \eta_4 < 1$, $\lambda = \frac{11}{56}$ and $F(x) = \ln x$. Consider the mapping $\alpha : Z \times Z \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ by

$$\alpha(x, y) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x > y \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}.$$

Let $S, T : Z \rightarrow Z$ be defined as

$$Sx = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} & \text{if } x \in A \\ \frac{x}{4} & \text{if } x \in B. \end{cases} \quad Tx = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{3} & \text{if } x \in A \\ \frac{x}{4} & \text{if } x \in B. \end{cases}$$

As $\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{3} \in Z, \alpha(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{3}) > 1$ taking $F(x) = \ln x$, for any $\tau \in (0, \frac{12}{95}]$. Then S and T satisfy the condition of Theorem 1.

If, we take $S = T$ in Theorem 1, then we are left with result.

Corollary 1. Let (Z, d_1) be a complete R.B.M.S with coefficient $b \geq 1$. Let $\alpha : Z \times Z \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ be a function and $S : Z \rightarrow Z$ be the α -dominated mapping on Z . Suppose that the following condition is satisfied:

There exist $\tau, \eta_1, \eta_2, \eta_3, \eta_4 > 0$ satisfying $b\eta_1 + b\eta_2 + (1 + b)b\eta_3 + \eta_4 < 1$ and a continuous and strictly increasing real function F such that

$$\tau + F(d_1(Se, Sy)) \leq F \left(\begin{aligned} &\eta_1 d_1(e, y) + \eta_2 d_1(e, Se) \\ &+ \eta_3 d_1(e, Sy) + \eta_4 \frac{d_1^2(e, Se) \cdot d_1(y, Sy)}{1 + d_1^2(e, y)} \end{aligned} \right), \tag{6}$$

whenever $e, y \in \{g_n\}, \alpha(e, y) \geq 1$ and $d_1(Se, Sy) > 0$ “where the sequence g_n is defined by g_0 arbitrary in $Z, g_{2n+1} = S^{2n}g_0$ ”. Then $\alpha(g_n, g_{n+1}) \geq 1$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$ and $\{g_n\} \rightarrow u \in Z$. Also, if the inequality (6) holds for u and either $\alpha(g_n, u) \geq 1$ or $\alpha(u, g_n) \geq 1$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$, then S and T have a common fixed point u in Z .

If, we take $\eta_2 = 0$ in Theorem 1, then we are left with the result.

Corollary 2. Let (Z, d_1) be a complete R.B.M.S with constant $b \geq 1$. Let $\alpha : Z \times Z \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ be a function and $S, T : Z \rightarrow Z$ be the α -dominated mappings on Z . Suppose that the following condition is satisfied:

There exist $\tau, \eta_1, \eta_3, \eta_4 > 0$ satisfying $b\eta_1 + (1 + b)b\eta_3 + \eta_4 < 1$ and a continuous and strictly increasing real function F such that

$$\tau + F(d_1(Se, Ty)) \leq F \left(\begin{matrix} \eta_1 d_1(e, y) + \eta_3 d_1(e, Ty) \\ + \eta_4 \frac{d_1^2(e, Se) \cdot d_1(y, Ty)}{1 + d_1^2(e, y)} \end{matrix} \right), \tag{7}$$

whenever $e, y \in \{g_n\}$, $\alpha(e, y) \geq 1$ and $d_1(Se, Ty) > 0$ “where the sequence g_n is defined by g_0 arbitrary in Z , $g_{2n+1} = S(TS)^n g_0$ and $g_{2n} = (TS)^{n+1} g_0$ ”. Then $\alpha(g_n, g_{n+1}) \geq 1$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$ and $\{g_n\} \rightarrow u \in Z$. Also, if the inequality (7) holds for u and either $\alpha(g_n, u) \geq 1$ or $\alpha(u, g_n) \geq 1$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$, then S and T have common fixed point u in Z .

If, we take $\eta_3 = 0$ in Theorem 1, then we are left with the result.

Corollary 3. Let (Z, d_1) be a complete R.B.M.S with constant $b \geq 1$. Let $\alpha : Z \times Z \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ be a function and $S, T : Z \rightarrow Z$ be the α -dominated mappings on Z . Suppose that the following condition is satisfied: There exist $\tau, \eta_1, \eta_2, \eta_4 > 0$ satisfying $b\eta_1 + b\eta_2 + \eta_4 < 1$ and a continuous and strictly increasing real function F such that

$$\tau + F(d_1(Se, Ty)) \leq F \left(\begin{matrix} \eta_1 d_1(e, y) + \eta_2 d_1(e, Se) \\ + \eta_4 \frac{d_1^2(e, Se) \cdot d_1(y, Ty)}{1 + d_1^2(e, y)} \end{matrix} \right), \tag{8}$$

whenever $e, y \in \{g_n\}$, $\alpha(e, y) \geq 1$ and $d_1(Se, Ty) > 0$ “where the sequence g_n is defined by g_0 arbitrary in Z , $g_{2n+1} = S(TS)^n g_0$ and $g_{2n} = (TS)^{n+1} g_0$ ”. Then $\alpha(g_n, g_{n+1}) \geq 1$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$ and $\{g_n\} \rightarrow u \in Z$. Also, if the inequality (8) holds for u and either $\alpha(g_n, u) \geq 1$ or $\alpha(u, g_n) \geq 1$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$, then S and T have common fixed point u in Z .

If, we take $\eta_4 = 0$ in Theorem 1, then we are left with the result.

Corollary 4. Let (Z, d_1) be a complete R.B.M.S with coefficient $b \geq 1$. Let $\alpha : Z \times Z \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ be a function and $S, T : Z \rightarrow Z$ be the α -dominated mappings on Z . Suppose that the following condition is satisfied:

There exist $\tau, \eta_1, \eta_2, \eta_3, \eta_4 > 0$ satisfying $b\eta_1 + b\eta_2 + (1 + b)b\eta_3 + \eta_4 < 1$ and a continuous and strictly increasing real function F such that

$$\tau + F(d_1(Se, Ty)) \leq F \left(\begin{matrix} \eta_1 d_1(e, y) + \eta_2 d_1(e, Se) \\ + \eta_3 d_1(e, Ty) \end{matrix} \right), \tag{9}$$

whenever $e, y \in \{g_n\}$, $\alpha(e, y) \geq 1$ and $d_1(Se, Ty) > 0$ “where the sequence g_n is defined by g_0 arbitrary in Z , $g_{2n+1} = S(TS)^n g_0$ and $g_{2n} = (TS)^{n+1} g_0$ ”, Then $\alpha(g_n, g_{n+1}) \geq 1$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$ and $\{g_n\} \rightarrow u \in Z$. Also, if the inequality (9) holds for u and either $\alpha(g_n, u) \geq 1$ or $\alpha(u, g_n) \geq 1$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$, then S and T have a common fixed point u in Z .

3. Fixed Points for Graphic Contractions

Lastly, we give a realization of Theorem 1 in graph theory. Jachymski, [14], shown the particular case for contraction mappings on metric space with a graph. Hussain et al. [12], introduced the concept of graphic contractions and obtained a point fixed result. Further results on graphic contraction can be seen in [8,21,27]. Shang [25], discussed briefly basic notions of graph limit theory and fix some necessary notations and presented many interesting applications.

Definition 6. Let Z be a nonempty set and $Q = (V(Q), W(Q))$ be a graph such that $V(Q) = Z$, $A \subseteq Z$. A mapping $S : Z \rightarrow Z$ is said to be a graph dominated on A if $(p, q) \in W(Q)$, for all $q \in Sp$ and $q \in A$.

Theorem 2. Let (Z, d_1) be a complete R.B.M.S endowed with a graph Q with coefficient $b \geq 1$. Let $S, T : Z \rightarrow Z$ be two self mappings. Suppose that the following satisfy:

(i) S and T are graph dominated on Z .

(ii) There exist $\tau, \eta_1, \eta_2, \eta_3, \eta_4 > 0$ satisfying $b\eta_1 + b\eta_2 + (1 + b)\eta_3 + \eta_4 < 1$ and a continuous and strictly increasing real function F such that

$$\tau + F(H_{d_1}(Sp, Tq)) \leq F \left(\begin{array}{c} \eta_1 d_1(p, q) + \eta_2 d_1(p, Sp) \\ + \eta_3 d_1(p, Tq) + \eta_4 \frac{d_1^2(p, Sp) \cdot d_1(q, Tq)}{1 + d_1^2(p, q)} \end{array} \right), \tag{10}$$

whenever $p, q \in \{g_n\}$, $(p, q) \in W(Q)$ and $d_1(Sp, Tq) > 0$ “where the sequence g_n is defined by g_0 arbitrary in Z , $g_{2n+1} = S(TS)^n g_0$ and $g_{2n} = (TS)^{n+1} g_0$ ”. Then $(g_n, g_{n+1}) \in W(Q)$ and $\{g_n\} \rightarrow m^*$. Also, if the inequality (10) holds for m^* and $(g_n, m^*) \in W(Q)$ or $(m^*, g_n) \in W(Q)$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$, then S and T have common fixed point m^* in Z .

Proof. Define, $\alpha : Z \times Z \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ by

$$\alpha(p, q) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } p \in Z, (p, q) \in W(Q) \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

As S and T are graph dominated on Z , then for $p \in Z$, $(p, q) \in W(Q)$ for all $q \in Sp$ and $(p, q) \in W(Q)$ for all $q \in Tp$. Therefore, $\alpha(p, q) = 1$ for all $q \in Sp$ and $\alpha(p, q) = 1$ for all $q \in Tp$. Hence $\alpha_*(p, Sp) = 1$, $\alpha_*(p, Tp) = 1$ for all $p \in Z$. Therefore, $S, T : Z \rightarrow Z$ are the α -dominated mappings on Z . Moreover, inequality (10) can be written as

$$\tau + F(H_{d_1}(Sp, Tq)) \leq F \left(\begin{array}{c} \eta_1 d_1(p, q) + \eta_2 d_1(p, Sp) \\ + \eta_3 d_1(p, Tq) + \eta_4 \frac{d_1^2(p, Sp) \cdot d_1(q, Tq)}{1 + d_1^2(p, q)} \end{array} \right)$$

whenever $p, q \in \{g_n\}$, $\alpha(p, q) \geq 1$ and $d_1(Sp, Tq) > 0$. Also, (ii) holds. Then, by Theorem 1, we have $\{g_n\} \rightarrow s^* \in Z$. Now, $g_n, s^* \in Z$ and either $(g_n, s^*) \in W(Q)$ or $(s^*, g_n) \in W(Q)$ implies that either $\alpha(g_n, s^*) \geq 1$ or $\alpha(s^*, g_n) \geq 1$. Therefore, all the conditions of Theorem 1 are satisfied. Hence, by Theorem 1, S and T have a common fixed point s^* in Z and $d_1(s^*, s^*) = 0$. \square

4. Conclusions

In the present work, we have achieved fixed-point results for new generalized F -contraction for a more general class of α -dominated mappings rather than α_* -admissible mappings and for a weaker class of strictly increasing mapping F rather than class of mappings F used by Wordowski [28]. We introduced the concept of a pair of graph-dominated mappings and given a fixed-point existence result of a fixed point for graphic contractions. Our results generalized and extended many recent fixed-point results of Rasham et al. [16,20], Wordowski’s result [28], Ameer et al. [6] and many classical results in the current literature (see [4,7,9,13,17,18,23,24]).

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